

FASTBLADE: A FATIGUE TESTING FACILITY FOR FULL-SCALE BLADES

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Keywords: Fatigue; Testing; Composites; Failure

ABSTRACT

Fatigue in composite tidal turbine blades presents a critical challenge for the long-term viability of tidal energy systems. These blades are subjected to millions of high-load cycles in harsh marine environments, and predicting their fatigue performance numerically is difficult due to complex material behaviour, loading conditions, and modelling assumptions. Offshore mechanical testing has emerged as a practical solution, enabling equivalent oceanic loads to be applied within accelerated timeframes in a controlled environment, thereby allowing for reliable structural assessments.

FastBlade, a unique facility developed by the University of Edinburgh, addresses longstanding issues in fatigue testing through a regenerative digital displacement hydraulic pump/motor system. This innovative approach enables precise, programmable cyclic loading of full-scale blades, resulting in up to 75% reduction in energy consumption compared to conventional hydraulic systems. FastBlade's platform is particularly suited for stiff composite structures that cannot be tested at resonance due to thermal limitations.

This paper, as part of the MaxBlade project, synthesises a review of research conducted at FastBlade, focusing on fatigue tests of a tidal blade using both single and multi-actuator configurations. Target hydrodynamic loads were derived from site-specific velocity data and simulated using Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) methods. During testing, the blade endured the equivalent of 20 years of tidal loading without catastrophic failure. However, variations in tip

displacements and strain responses across different actuator configurations highlighted the importance of refined load introduction methods and monitoring strategies.

Analysis of the test data informs improvements in control algorithms, actuator coordination, sensor placement, and calibration techniques. These enhancements enhance the reliability and repeatability of fatigue tests, contributing to the development of more robust and efficient blade designs. FastBlade's approach demonstrates the future of sustainable structural testing and offers broader applications across marine, wind, aerospace, and civil sectors.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing urgency to transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy has led to a surge of interest in marine energy systems, particularly tidal stream turbines. Tidal energy offers a unique advantage: it is a predictable and consistent source of power that complements intermittent sources, such as solar and wind [1]. As global energy systems evolve, the tidal energy sector is poised to play a critical role, especially in coastal regions with strong and reliable tidal currents [2].

The tidal energy industry traces its roots to early installations such as the La Rance tidal barrage in France (1967) [3]. Since then, advances in technology—particularly horizontal axis tidal turbines (HATs)—have enabled more practical, scalable, and less environmentally intrusive solutions [4]. The potential for tidal stream energy to contribute up to 100 GW to the EU grid by 2050 underscores its strategic importance [5]. However, realising this potential requires addressing key engineering challenges, most notably the structural reliability and fatigue life of turbine blades operating in a dense, high-load marine environment [6-7].

Tidal turbine blades must withstand millions of load cycles in harsh underwater conditions characterised by strong currents, turbulence, and biofouling. The risk of structural failure is significant, with consequences that extend beyond repair costs to include downtime and safety issues [8]. Unfortunately, much of the data informing blade design remains proprietary, and in situ testing, though valuable, is limited by uncontrolled environmental variables. Hydrodynamic model testing in flumes or tanks, such as at the FloWave facility in Edinburgh [9-10], provides controlled insight at a more minor scale, but cannot replicate the full complexity of real-world, full-scale blade behaviour [11-12].

To address these limitations, full-scale fatigue testing has emerged as an essential tool. Among recent advancements, the FastBlade facility in Scotland represents a significant leap forward [13]. Utilising a regenerative digital displacement hydraulic actuation system, FastBlade enables precise and energy-efficient cyclic loading of full-scale blades [14-15]. In 2022, FastBlade conducted high-load tests simulating over 21 years of tidal cycles, both with single- and triple-actuator setups, and continued testing until blade failure occurred, thereby setting a new benchmark in composite blade validation [13, 16, 17].

FastBlade's design directly addresses the inefficiencies of conventional servo-hydraulic rigs, particularly for stiff composite blades that cannot be excited at resonance without thermal damage. The facility's integration of simulation technologies, digital twins, and advanced monitoring further exemplifies a new paradigm in structural validation [18].

This paper synthesises research from across FastBlade's development and testing campaigns. Specifically, we investigate the structural performance and fatigue behaviour of a full-scale composite tidal turbine blade under both static and fatigue loading. We compare blade responses under single- and multiple-actuator configurations, examining how load frequency and control strategies affect displacement and strain. The study aims to inform future improvements in blade testing, design validation, and certification practices, supporting the development of more efficient and reliable tidal energy systems.

2 OVERVIEWS OF THE FASTBLADE FACILITY

FastBlade, located in Rosyth, Scotland, is the world's first test facility to implement regenerative digital displacement hydraulics designed explicitly for the large-scale fatigue testing of long, stiff composite structures, such as tidal turbine blades measuring between 2 and 14 meters. The facility enables both accelerated fatigue and static loading, providing high-fidelity data on structural performance under simulated real-world marine conditions. It can resist a moment of up to 11.96 MNm and a shear load of 2.13 MN in static tests, as well as a moment of 4.70 MNm and a shear load of 0.94 MN during accelerated fatigue tests.

At the heart of FastBlade is a 70-tonne reaction frame (see Figure 1), engineered to withstand substantial loads during both static and dynamic fatigue tests. The structural setup includes a reaction plane, support wall, T-Slot bed plates, and a custom adaptor plate, all anchored on bridge bearings recessed into a 2.5-meter-deep floor pit, ensuring stability and repeatability during high-load testing scenarios.

Figure 1: General arrangement and dimensions of the reaction frame at FastBlade. (a) Top view, (b) Lateral view, and (c) General view [13].

The facility's hydraulic actuation system is powered by four Digital DisplacementTM reversible pumps developed by Danfoss. These pumps deliver a reversible hydraulic flow rate of 880 litres per minute, enabling precise actuator control and the simulation of complex ocean interaction loads. Additionally, the regenerative nature of the hydraulic system allows energy recovery, making FastBlade up to 75% more energy-efficient than conventional hydraulic testing systems of a similar scale. FastBlade is a cutting-edge platform designed not only to validate the structural integrity of tidal blades but also to support the advancement of sustainable marine energy technologies through efficient, data-rich, and environmentally conscious testing methodologies.

3 ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND HYDRAULIC INNOVATION

FastBlade's hydraulic innovation lies in its use of Digital Displacement Pump (DDPMs) [19], which form the backbone of its regenerative hydraulic actuation system (see Figure 2). Unlike traditional servo-valve hydraulic setups, which lose significant energy as heat during load cycling, DDPMs offer a smarter, energy-efficient alternative. These digitally controlled units dynamically regulate flow and pressure by precisely timing valve openings in sync with the rotating shaft, eliminating the need for energy-wasting throttling.

Figure 2: Digital Displacement Pumps and Motors at FastBlade.

A key advantage of this system is its ability to recover and reuse energy. During cyclic loading, the mechanical energy that would typically be dissipated is instead captured from the rotating inertia of the hydraulic drive and fed back into the system. This bidirectional flow capability means the actuators can alternate between applying loads and harvesting energy, depending on the structural response of the test specimen, as shown in Figure 3 for a test in which the power from the grid was cut and the system ran solely on the accumulated inertia.

This innovation results in energy savings of up to 75%, making FastBlade significantly more efficient than conventional fatigue testing systems. Such efficiency is particularly valuable when testing large, thick composite structures, such as tidal turbine blades, where resonant testing is impractical due to high damping properties and the risk of thermal buildup [20]. In addition to reducing power consumption, the regenerative system also enables more prolonged and more intensive test campaigns without compromising sustainability. The precise control afforded by DDPMs allows engineers to replicate complex, real-world marine load conditions, including quasi-steady flows and asymmetric stresses, while minimising environmental impact.

Figure 3: In the regeneration test, power to the VLT (Variable Load Terminal) is cut at 5 seconds. (a) The loading cycle continues even without power, with the amplitude gradually decreasing. After 25 cycles, the transferred energy drops to about one-third of its original level. (b) The motor slows down once power is cut. If loading is also stopped, the system slows down smoothly (as shown by the red trace). If loading continues, the motor decelerates slightly faster. This slight difference shows the high energy recovery (round-trip efficiency) of the system. (c) The energy transferred between the flywheel and the load also decreases over time, though not in a classic exponential (logarithmic) pattern. For the first 3 seconds after the power cut, the energy remains relatively steady, as the flywheel supplies the required power. [19].

5 FATIGUE TESTING

FastBlade enables accelerated life-cycle testing of full-scale composite tidal blades using static and fatigue test protocols aligned with IEC TS 62600-3 [21]. Tests are run at non-resonant frequencies to prevent internal heating, particularly for thick-sectioned tidal blades made of carbon or glass-fibre composites. Advanced sensing technologies such as strain gauges, DIC, and embedded instrumentation capture strain localisation, damage progression, and global stiffness. Actuators apply loads in both single-point and multi-point configurations to replicate the hydrodynamic moments observed in real-world deployments.

The 5.25 m long tidal turbine blade, tested, with a cross-section based on the NACA 63-4XX aerofoil series, was initially designed by Tidal Generation Limited and manufactured by Aviation Enterprises Limited for the DeepGen project. It came from a decommissioned 500 kW tidal stream turbine that operated at EMEC's Fall of Warness site for approximately two years. Some original design documents were unavailable, and Airborne has since acquired the design rights. Structurally, the blade features an 8 mm-thick glass-fibre skin, 3 mm GFRP ribs, and a spar cap made of 75% unidirectional carbon fibre epoxy prepreg. $\pm 45^\circ$ carbon fibre epoxy shear webs provide additional torsional strength. A rear GFRP spar, positioned 100 mm from the trailing edge, helps reduce peel stresses and improve fatigue performance.

To obtain the testing loads, high-fidelity simulations are a central component of FastBlade's methodology [22]. Actuator line modelling and RANS-based CFD simulations derive realistic load distributions from site-specific data. This includes modelling flow shear during ebb and flood tides and translating it into spatially and temporally varying blade loads (see Figure 4). These simulations guide the placement of actuators and force profiles. Furthermore, synthetic resonance, a method that mimics structural response through non-resonant actuation, bridges the gap between real-world conditions and laboratory constraints. This simulation-informed testing reduces the risk of over-conservatism and allows designers to optimise blade mass, stiffness, and geometry.

Figure 4: Hydrodynamic Simulation Results. The azimuthal variation of the normalized blade root bending moments in (a) the flapwise and (b) edgewise directions is depicted for both flood (blue) and ebb (red) tides. The rotor operates at a hub-height flow speed of $U=2.8$ m/s. [13]

The blade was tested under different setups (see Figure 5), following [21], the natural frequency was taken at the beginning and the end of the entire test program in setup (see Figure 5(a)), later on, the blade was tested with a single actuator which is a conventional test setup (see Figure 5(b)), a three actuator setup (see Figure 5(c)) to compare the benefits and challenges of more contact points as shown in [8] and finally a three actuator setup for extreme loads (see Figure 5(d)). The root bending moments for setups 5b and 5c were 1000 kNm for the static test and 650 kNm for the fatigue test. Nevertheless, after approximately 120000 cycles, the loads were changed to test different clamping system materials (see [24]) and evaluate the blade's response to higher load fatigue cycles. For setup 6d, the root bending moments during the static tests were up to 1400, 1600, 1800, and 3060 kNm. For fatigue with configuration 6d, first, a series of cycles at 1330 kN.m (almost twice the mean water velocity load) is applied to scale up to 1750 kN.m (nearly 2.7 times the mean water velocity load).

Figure 5: Testing setups. (a) No actuators for natural frequency, (b) Single actuator, (c) three actuators for design loads, (d) three actuators for extreme loads.

Testing credibility is reinforced through statistical validation techniques. FastBlade integrates real-time Process Capability Indices (PCIs) to monitor how closely the applied loads match prescribed values [15]. Load traces from historic and real-time data are compared to identify anomalies and deviations. These metrics ensure traceability, allowing engineers to diagnose actuator drift or calibration errors. Combined with redundant sensors, specialised anomaly detection algorithms[23] and automated control systems, this statistical approach guarantees repeatable and certifiable test outcomes, aligning with emerging marine energy certification frameworks. As a result of these controls, the results of displacement and root bending moments for the different fatigue tests are presented in Figure 6.

FastBlade has significantly advanced the understanding of tidal turbine blade mechanics under operational conditions. The research outputs inform the development of the next generation of certification standards, reduce design conservatism, and enable predictive maintenance strategies. FastBlade's principles, energy-efficient actuation, integrated simulation, and digital intelligence are extendable to aerospace wings, bridge components, offshore platforms, and wind turbine blades. As such, the facility serves as a model for structural testing in high-capital, high-reliability industries. Using all these valuable lessons, FastBlade approaches the new MaxBlade project.

Figure 6: . Results from the different fatigue tests. The vertical black lines indicate a static test. The colour blue indicates the single actuator test, the colour red indicates the use of 3 actuators, and the colour yellow indicates the use of 3 actuators for high loads: (a) Root Bending Moment at the crest of each cycle, (b) Twice the amplitude of the Root Bending Moment at each cycle (c) Displacement at the blade's centre during the crest of each cycle, (d) Displacement at the blade's tip during the crest of each cycle, (e) Relation between displacement at the blade's centre and the root bending moment during the crest of each cycle, and (f) Relation between displacement at the blade's tip and the root bending moment during the crest of each cycle.

9 CONCLUSIONS

FastBlade represents a significant advancement in structural testing for tidal energy systems. By combining regenerative hydraulic actuation, simulation-informed load design, and advanced monitoring systems, it enables efficient and realistic fatigue testing of full-scale composite blades. The facility's use of digital displacement pump/motors (DDPMs) reduces energy consumption by up to 75%, making long-duration, high-load testing both feasible and cost-effective, particularly for stiff, high-damping structures where resonant testing is impractical.

Through a combination of static and fatigue tests, FastBlade has demonstrated the ability to simulate decades of tidal loading in a matter of weeks. Configurable actuator setups and precise control systems allow replication of realistic hydrodynamic moments, while embedded instrumentation provides valuable data on strain, displacement, and damage progression.

Simulation plays a key role in test planning, with hydrodynamic loads derived from RANS-based models and actuator line methods that capture the complex effects of tidal direction and flow shear. These simulations ensure that laboratory loads reflect real-world operational conditions. Quality assurance is further enhanced through statistical control tools such as Process Capability Indices, which support consistent and traceable testing.

The integration of digital twin technology adds a forward-looking dimension to FastBlade's approach. These models, ranging from data-driven to physics-informed, enable predictive insights, inform control strategies, and offer potential pathways for real-time condition monitoring of deployed blades.

Overall, FastBlade provides a practical and forward-compatible platform for validating the structural integrity of tidal turbine blades. Its contributions extend beyond marine energy, offering applicable methodologies for other sectors requiring high-fidelity fatigue testing. As the industry continues to evolve, facilities like FastBlade will play a crucial role in supporting safer, more efficient, and cost-effective renewable energy solutions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All the authors: the MaxBlade project funded via the Horizon Europe MaxBlade project (Grant No. 101096891), co-funded by United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) and the European Commission.

All the authors: the Supergen ORE Hub for funding received through the Flexible Fund Award FF2020-1063

M. Munko: Babcock International and The Data Lab for research funding.

M.A. Valdivia-Camacho: Wind & Marine Energy Systems & Structures (WAMESS) CDT under the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council grant agreement EP/S023801/1.

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